

SCREENING COMPOSITES MATERIALS BASED ON GRAPHITE FILLERS.

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SUMMARY: Conducting composites were prepared basing upon thermosplitted graphite and series binder: rubber, polyvinyl chloride and silicoorganic compounds aiming at materials screening UHF radiation. Conductivity of the obtained materials varied depending on a concentration of filler, on a type of a binder and preparative technology and lied in the limits $1 \div 10^3 \Omega^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$. Experimental frequency characteristics of the screening coefficients coincided with theoretically expected ones.

KEYWORDS: composites, graphite and related compounds, screening materials.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials with conducting fillers are not going to displace the traditional materials (metals and semiconductors), however, in many cases they present adequate materials for protection of electronic equipment against electromagnetic radiation [1,2]. One of the most urgent tasks of the contemporary materials science is development and studies of electrophysical properties of polymeric filled compositions.

The purpose of the present work has been to develop composite materials based on the thermo-splitted graphite (TSG) and to evaluate the screening properties of corresponding material in high frequency diapason.

EXPERIMENTAL

The screening coefficient in a remote zone, which is defined as a ratio of the actual value of the electric field potential $|E_2^*|$ at a chosen point in absence of a screen to one $|E_1^*|$ at the same point behind the screen, has been used for an evaluation of the functional properties of a screen.

$$K_{sc} = -20 \cdot \lg_{10} \left| \frac{E_2^*}{E_1^*} \right| = -20 \cdot \lg_{10} \left| \frac{H_2^*}{H_1^*} \right| \quad (1)$$

Measurements of a screening coefficient have been conducted applying the wave-guide technique in a frequency diapason $8 \div 12.4$ GHz. An automated complex has been assembled basing on a panoramic meter of a standing wave coefficient (R2-61, Russia) and lock-in-

amplifier (model 5210, "EGG/PAR").

DC-conductivity was being defined over standard four or two electrode technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Modeling.

Radiation absorption as connected with an absorption of electromagnetic energy in the screen, a value of losses due to reflection of an electromagnetic wave from both sides of the screen, and a value connected with multiple reflections inside the screen are three main components defining the screening efficiency. Account for various channels of energy dissipation in a sample of a thickness d , namely: complex permittivity: $\epsilon^* = \epsilon' + j\epsilon'' = \epsilon' + j\sigma/\omega$ (σ – conductivity, ω – circular frequency) and permeability: $\mu^* = \mu' + j\mu''$ leads to the following expression used here for the screening coefficient:

$$K_{sc} = 20 \ln \left| ch(\gamma^* d) + \frac{1 + Z_{rel}^2}{2Z_{rel}} \cdot sh(\gamma^* d) \right| \quad (2)$$

where $Z_{rel} = Z^*/Z_0$, Z_0 – a wave resistance of a medium to which the plate of a material is placed:

$$Z^* = \frac{j\omega\mu^*}{\gamma^*}; \quad \gamma^* = j\sqrt{\omega^2\epsilon^*\mu^* - \left(\frac{\pi}{a}\right)^2} \quad \text{for wave-guide mode, } a - \text{geometric parameter.}$$

An increase of the portion of energy reflected from a screen for high conductivity is a classic way for an increase of a screening ability of a material. As a rule magnetic susceptibility is a dominating factor at frequencies below about 1 MHz, and conductivity of a material is one above 1 MHz. The Eqn. 2 may be reduced to:

$$K_{sc} = 20 \ln |1 + 188 \cdot \sigma \cdot d| \quad (3)$$

for thin conducting films of non-magnetic materials in vacuum (air) under normal wave incidence.

The Eqn. 3 indicates a contribution of an ohmic conductivity into screening coefficient. An increase of the portion of energy reflected from a screen for high conductivity is a classic way for an increase of a screening ability of a material. However, in a number of cases it is impossible to prepare the material where the required physical and mechanical properties (e.g., high elasticity) coincide with a sufficient conductivity.

Experimental.

Thermoexpanded graphite (TEG) with a powder density of ≈ 16 g/l was used as conducting filler in present study. List material of pure TEG was prepared by rolling in a calander with variable gap. Such material exhibits conductivity up to $2 \cdot 10^3 \Omega^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ and may be used, e.g., for radiation tightness bushings in high frequency instrumentation.

Elastic conducting composite materials pose a special interest. A series of composite materials has been studied, where a synthetic rubber is used as a binder for TEG. Composition based on TEG and rubber was prepared by mixing of rubber solution in light petroleum with TEG in presence of dicumil peroxide at rotor evaporator till formation of a flowing powder. Upon drying the composition, the samples of material were pressed keeping them for 30 minutes under pressure 200 kg/cm^2 at temperature $140 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. DC conductivity of the prepared materials was changing from 2 to $200 \Omega^{-1} \cdot \text{cm}^{-1}$ (Table 1) under variation of the conducting filler from 20 to 80 % mass. Having such conductivity values it was possible to prepare elastic bulk

materials having a screening coefficient, K_{sc} above 30 dB at sample thickness below 1 mm.

As far as screening composite films, in this study materials prepared by mixing of plastified polyvinylchloride (PVC) with TEG and subsequent caladering of a mixture at temperatures $110 \div 130$ °C were obtained and investigated as samples. Experimental results for HFR transparency coefficients for samples of PVC filled with TEG are shown in Fig. 2.

Table 1: Conductivity of TEG-based composite materials.

TEG conc., mass.%	Conductivity of a composite, σ ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}$) ⁻¹
20	$2 \cdot 10^0$
30	$5 \cdot 10^0$
60	$8 \cdot 10^1$
80	$2 \cdot 10^2$

Fig. 2. Experimental data on amplitude-frequency characteristics of a screening coefficient for PVC-TEG filled composite materials.

CONCLUSION

Conducting composite materials with as TEG developed in present paper may be used for bushings in constructions of electronic and communication instrumentation for protection of printed circles against electromagnetic radiation. Such materials in combination with other conducting and magnetic materials can be used for development of various means of an individual and collective protection against SHF-radiation [3].

REFERENCES

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